

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF LOGISTICS TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article analysis investigates the integral and differential characteristic of English and Uzbek logistics phrases as they are appear in translation terms reflecting new semantic meanings of the terminological system, the challenge of adequate translation of English and Uzbek logistics terms brought into the terminological system based on cognition that has become essential at this time. The importance of producing a bilingual English and Uzbek dictionary of logistics terminology is stressed in given materials.

Key words: *logistics phrases, transportation, logistic terminologies, linguistic structure, morphemes, terminology system, definitional framework*

The existence of language processes in the field of logistic terminology naturally proves that terms are treated as units of language. One of the key goals of transportation systems is to develop new meanings of existing terminologies in the field of special transportation logistics. Because logistics is a multifaceted phenomenon with multiple meanings, the linguistic structure of a word is critical in identifying terms linked to logistics. A word's meaning is the same as that of many others in one or more general groups called grammatical categories.

There is a semantic connection between the meanings of multiple meanings phrases in the English and Uzbek terminology systems for logistics operations. If there is no or a weak connection, terms with the same character may represent a semantic relationship. Morphemes are lexical units with similar but distinct spelling and reading meanings.

The following aspect of homonymy is frequently recognized according to lexicological and lexicographic classifications that morphemes are always words in different forms and only in the course of historical development have words with equal

phonetic and matching speech sounds for different phonetic and usually random reasons. When a multiple meanings word is denied to have two or more lexical units, it is important to detect units that share the same speech sound but belong to separate parts of speech, such as:

Carrier – “*kema yoki boshqa bir transport vositasi*”

A firm that provides transportation services, typically owning and operating transportation equipment. Examples include:

- *trucking company (yuk tashishga asoslangan tashkilot)*
- *railroad (temir yo'l)*
- *airline (havo yo'li)*
- *steamship line (dengiz kemasi vositasi)*
- *parcel/express company (posilka/maxsus tezkor tashkilot)*

The term "terminology" actually refers to a specific field. It is important to consider the meanings of phrases used in each language. The phrase **Carrier** displays lexical combination, for example, is interpreted in special dictionaries as follows:

1. The organization supplies the services for owning the products not having yet made or delivered in a previous period of time.
2. The firm order to operate the item that cannot be dispatched with the rest of the items or was not shipped at all.
3. Product was transported however was out of transportation equipment that was promised for being shipped as soon as it became available.

Loss and damage – “*yo'qotish va zarar*”

Loss or **damage** of freight shipments while in transit or in a carrier-operated warehouse. Terms for the handling of claims are usually stipulated in the freight bill. Shippers/consignees usually take out insurance against L&D with premiums a function of the value of goods shipped, and the likelihood of L&D.

Terminal – “*yakuniy-boshlang'ich bekat; vokzal*”

Transportation facility with one or more of the following roles:

1. System access: terminals are points at which freight enters and leaves the transportation system.

2. Freight consolidation/distribution
3. Mode transfer: freight may change from one mode to another, for example, rail to truck.
4. Vehicle transfer: within a single mode, freight may transfer from one vehicle to another.
5. Storage and warehousing
6. Fleet maintenance

Freight size – “*yuk hajmi*”

Freight is most often measured by its weight, and transportation vehicles of varying sizes typically have weight capacities that cannot be exceeded due to engineering or regulatory reasons. Freight may also be measured by cube, which generally refers to the volume of the freight. A vehicle is said to cube-out if it does not exceed its weight capacity, but its volume is completely full.

Containers, chassis, and vans (trailers) – “*konteyner, shassi, furgon (treylar)*”

Standard trucking companies use vans (or trailers) to move standard dry goods. These trailers consist of a storage box that is permanently attached to a set of wheels (the set of wheels is often known as a truck). Intermodal ocean containers are moved on the road by attaching them to a separate piece of equipment, a chassis, which is essentially a set of wheels on a lightweight frame.

Box-Jenkins Model: In time series analysis, the Box–Jenkins methodology applies autoregressive moving average models to find the best fit of a time series to past values of this time series, in order to make forecasts. See: Forecast.

Boxcar – “*vagon*”

An enclosed rail car typically 40 to 50 feet long; used for packaged freight and some bulk commodities.

Here, we can see some abbreviations which are used in sphere of logistics term and terminology:

- BMP: e.g. Bitmap Imagine
- BPM: e.g. Business Performance Measurement
- BPO: e.g. Business Process Outsourcing
- BPR: e.g. Business Process Reengineering
- BRs: e.g. Business Reviews.

It is clear from the sources in English and Uzbek that the ambiguity aspects of both languages are intertwined expressed equally. Another very broad one that belongs to this field distributed business plan combination in English and Uzbek we see the equality of polysemantic properties:

1) A statement of long-range strategy and revenue, cost, and profit objectives usually accompanied by budgets, a projected balance sheet, and a cash flow (source and application of funds) statement. A business plan is usually stated in terms of dollars and grouped by product family. The business plan is then translated into synchronized tactical functional plans through the production planning process (or the sales and operations planning process). Although frequently stated in different terms (dollars versus units), these tactical plans should agree with each other and with the business plan. See: long-term planning, strategic plan.

2) A document consisting of the business details (organization, strategy, and financing tactics) prepared by an entrepreneur to plan for a new business.

1) daromadlar, xarajatlar va foyda uchun uzoq muddatli strategiya va maqsadlar to'g'risidagi bayonot, odatda byudjetlar, prognoz qilingan balans va pul oqimlari to'g'risidagi hisobot (mablag'larning manbasi va ishlatilishi). Biznes-reja odatda dollar bilan ifodalanadi va mahsulot guruhi bo'yicha guruhlanadi. Keyinchalik biznes-reja ishlab chiqarishni rejalashtirish jarayonida (yoki sotish va operatsiyalarni rejalashtirish jarayonida) sinxronlashtirilgan taktik funksional rejalarga aylantiriladi. Ushbu taktik rejalar ko'pincha turli xil atamalar bilan ifodalangan bo'lsada (birliklarga nisbatan dollar), ular bir- biriga va biznes-rejaga muvofiq bo'lishi kerak. Qarang: uzoq muddatli rejalashtirish, strategik reja;

2) tadbirkor tomonidan yangi biznesni rejalashtirish uchun tayyorlangan tafsilotlar (tashkilot, strategiya va moliyalashtirish taktikalari)dan iborat hujjat

From the comments in English and Uzbek above, it can be seen that the meanings in both languages are the same. The number of one can also correspond in terms of content.

The definitional framework of logistics in English and Uzbek and the main problems in converting logistics terms were recognized, as well as the most effective ways of solving them; methods of translating terms were studied, and logistics was found to be the most acceptable and common in terms of terminology. The fundamental challenge in attaining scientific and business translation equivalency is illuminating the original substance of the document using the linguistic system of the transferred translation.

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